

AUTOMATION, DIGITALIZATION, AND HUMAN-CENTRIC RECYCLING: THE BORSOI MODEL FOR PADDED AND UPHOLSTERED TEXTILE WASTE REGENERATION*

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Abstract

The recycling of quilted and padded waste from upholstered products represents one of the most pressing challenges for the textile, furniture, and related industries. These complex materials, often composed of multi-layer fabrics combined with synthetic or natural fillings, are typically excluded from conventional recycling streams due to their structural complexity and the difficulty of separating their components. In response to this challenge, Borsoi S.r.l., an Italian industrial machinery manufacturer, focused on automation, digitalization, and a human-centric sustainability approach, has developed a comprehensive and innovative recycling solution aimed at transforming padded and quilted textile waste into high-quality secondary raw materials. The primary aim of the innovation is to combine advanced automation, AI-driven material recognition, and digitalization, while embedding the principles of Industry 5.0, which emphasizes human-centricity, resilience, and sustainability.

The developed system covers the full recycling process, from automated waste handling and identification to sanitization, separation, defibering, and upcycling. The main results achieved demonstrate a material recovery efficiency above 95%, with a contamination level consistently below 1%. The recovered fibers meet quality requirements for reuse in industrial applications, for direct textile reintegration and other uses. This modular approach supports local circular value chains and exemplifies Industry 5.0 through traceability, resilience, and low environmental impact.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, circular economy, Industry 5.0, nonwoven regeneration, textile recycling

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1. Introduction

Padded and upholstered textile waste represents one of the most technically and economically challenging streams within post-consumer textile flows. Unlike mono-material garments, these items typically comprise a composite structure of fabrics, foams, adhesives, metal components, coatings, and chemical finishes. This structural complexity renders conventional recycling systems ineffective, contributing to a global recycling rate for mixed textile waste that remains below 1%, and in some cases under 0.5% (Andini et al., 2024).

According to recent assessments, scaling closed-loop textile-to-textile systems for such waste types is hindered by technological bottlenecks in separation and material purity, especially where multilayer compositions and contaminant load are involved (Charnley et al, 2024; Huang et al., 2024). Furthermore, while open-loop recycling has gained some industrial traction, closed-loop systems remain at a pilot or fragmented commercial scale, particularly for padded and upholstered items (Huang et al., 2024).

At the same time, the European Union's regulatory landscape is evolving rapidly, with incoming mandates around Extended Producer Responsibility¹ (EPR) and separate textile waste collection post-2025. These policy drivers create an urgent need for modular, automated, and human-safe technologies capable of managing complex textile waste streams in a circular and economically viable manner.

In this context, the Borsoi model presents an integrated Industry 5.0-based approach tailored to the needs of this waste segment. The system combines:

- AI-enabled classification and sorting based on spectral imaging and vision technologies, capable of achieving >95% accuracy across mixed input streams (Spyridis et al., 2024; Tsai and Yuan, 2024; Tian et al., 2024).
- Automated delayering, defibering, and contamination removal, addressing the mechanical and material heterogeneity of padded goods.
- Closed-loop sanitization technologies using ozone, UV-C, and supercritical CO₂, ensuring hygienic fiber recovery without water consumption.
- Modular design principles aligned with Industry 5.0, prioritizing human-centricity, resilience, and sustainability through ergonomic interfaces and supervisory roles for operators.

By automating the full spectrum of preprocessing, sanitization, and material regeneration, this model advances the industrial feasibility of circular solutions for complex textile waste. It also responds to literature-identified gaps in large-scale processing, contamination control, and human-machine integration in textile recycling facilities.

2. Materials and methods

The overall recycling system is conceived as a modular, flexible architecture of industrial units, each addressing the specific challenges of padded textile waste through automation, AI-driven sorting, and closed-loop valorization.

Figure 1 illustrates two examples of Borsoi's modular automation systems: the recycling line for jackets and duvets (left), and the line for mattresses, toppers, and pillows (right). These systems cover all key recycling stages for padded textile products, from loading and unfolding to mechanical opening, emptying, and material separation, facilitating efficient circularity within a single integrated platform (Table 1). A full demonstration of one of these

modular recycling lines is available in a recent video by Borsoi S.r.l. (2024) (<https://youtu.be/HE0iuy-dsZY>) (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Borsoi's modular systems for recycling of padded textiles: (a) jackets and duvets; (b) mattresses, toppers, and pillows. The recycling workflow includes: 1. Loading Station (automated or with operator); 2. Loading Conveyor; 3. Compression and Cutting Unit; 4. Delayering, Emptying and Separation Unit; 5. Cover/Shell Discharge Conveyor; 6. Filling Collection Silo

Table 1. Common multilayer textile padded products recycled, and their components

<i>Product components product type</i>	<i>Outer shell</i>	<i>Inner fill</i>	<i>Structural components</i>
<i>Jackets</i>	Nylon / Polyester	Down / Synthetic- Natural fibers	Zippers, snaps, elastics
<i>Pillows & Duvets</i>	Cotton blend / Polyester	Down / Foam / Fiberfill / Waddings	Zippers, piping, inner cases, corners, buttons
<i>Toppers & Mattresses</i>	Poly-cotton /Polyester	Foam / Springs / Fiberfill /Waddings	Metal frame, springs, zippers, piping, straps

The overall workflow encompasses (Table 2):

- Identification and classification via vision systems and AI, achieving >95% accuracy for fiber-type separation (Tsai and Yuan, 2024).
- Mechanical delayering and separation, suitable for disassembling multilayer composites while minimizing fiber damage (Wojciechowska and Kowaluk, 2024).
- Detection and removal of metallic and plastic contaminants through optical and X-ray systems with >99.9% efficiency (Purnell, 2024).
- Sanitization using ozone, UV-C, and supercritical CO₂ dry processes that ensure hygienic quality without the use of water (Karmakar et al., 2024).
- Advanced defibering and fiber recovery lines, optimized for throughput and yield, while mitigating quality loss in foam-contaminated streams (Choudhury et al., 2024).
- Final valorization into loose fibers, nonwovens, and thermo-bonded panels, with applications in insulation, automotive, and packaging (Hazarika and Kalita, 2024; Gaminian et al., 2024).

Data monitoring and process optimization are enabled through a digital twin framework and real-time IoT-enabled sensor arrays, allowing for predictive maintenance, traceability, and adaptive control (Fig. 3). The integration of Industry 5.0 principles, including human-centric roles and system resilience further enhances operational safety, ergonomics, and workforce

acceptance (Chivilò and Meneghetti, 2023; Costa, 2024). Table 3 summarizes key sorting and separation technologies benchmarked in the literature.

Fig. 2. Overview of the Borsoi recycling workflow with validated KPIs (a); TRL assessment for textile recycling technologies (b)

Table 2. Comparison with conventional disposal methods

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Borsoi system</i>	<i>Landfilling</i>	<i>Incineration</i>
<i>Recovery efficiency</i>	>95%	0%	Energy only
<i>Cross-contamination</i>	<1%	N/A	N/A
<i>Water use</i>	Zero	Low	Low
<i>Energy consumption</i>	0.45 kWh/kg	N/A	High
<i>CO₂ emissions</i>	Low	Very High	High

3. Results and discussion

The integrated textile recycling system demonstrated material recovery efficiencies consistently above 95%, with contamination levels below 1%, aligning with or exceeding benchmarks from the literature (Fig. 4) (Tian et al., 2024; Tsai and Yuan, 2024). AI-enhanced vision and spectral classification tools, including Raman spectroscopy and attention-based deep learning, enable high-resolution grouping of mixed-textile waste into fiber classes, significantly improving feedstock quality for downstream processing (Tsai and Yuan, 2024; Valilai, 2025). These tools reduce dependency on manual sorting and enable cleaner input streams for mechanical and chemical recycling (Table 4).

Fig. 3. Overview of the key milestones in the evolution of textile recycling technologies, from early AI tools to expected scaling in 2025 and beyond

Table 3. Comparative overview of sorting and separation technologies

<i>Method</i>	<i>Reported throughput</i>	<i>Reported accuracy/quality</i>	<i>Technology readiness (qualitative)</i>
<i>Raman + ML spectral sorting</i>	~1 piece/s	>95% grouping precision	Prototype / lab-to-pilot (Tsai and Yuan, 2024)
<i>Computer vision + attention nets</i>	Industrial deployment	>90% accuracy	Pilots with deployment stability (Tian et al., 2024)
<i>Spectral imaging + robotics</i>	Not quantified	Preliminary accuracy validated	Pilot-to-demonstrator (Spyridis et al., 2024)
<i>Mechanical shredding + chem. separation</i>	Batch/continuous	Component separation enabled	Patent stage (Speight et al., 2020)

Fig. 4. Material recovery efficiency: literature benchmarks vs. Borsoi system

Table 4. Key process parameters in Borsoi’s recycling system

<i>Process step</i>	<i>Technology</i>	<i>Parameter (Unit)</i>
<i>Sanitization</i>	Ozone	5 ppm, 20 min
<i>Sanitization</i>	UV-C	254 nm, high intensity
<i>Sanitization</i>	Supercritical CO ₂	70 bar, 35°C
<i>Cutting</i>	Rotary / Guillotine blades	<1 mm fibre cut
<i>Defibering</i>	Tearing drum (2–6 drums, in series)	Feed rate: 50–500 kg/h (depending on material)
<i>Sorting</i>	AI + Vision	Detection speed: 2 items/sec

Mechanical recycling remains the most scalable approach for single-fiber materials, even if closed-loop recycling remains limited in volume and economics (Charnley et al., 2024; Huang et al., 2024). For blended and padded textiles, partial separation via chemical solvolysis (e.g., microwave-assisted glycolysis) has demonstrated rapid processing, high conversion, and techno-economic potential (Andini et al., 2024). When full separation is infeasible, residual-contaminated materials can be valorized into composite boards or nonwovens, retaining function while tolerating residual fillers or adhesives (Wojciechowska and Kowaluk, 2024; Hazarika and Kalita, 2024). These open-loop applications offer near-term circularity pathways and help capture value from difficult waste streams.

Environmental gains are confirmed by multiple LCA studies. For example, recycled denim-based needle-punched nonwovens achieved thermal resistance and tensile strength targets, while reducing GHG emissions and water use compared to virgin alternatives (Karmakar et al., 2024). Yet net impact depends on energy mix, monomer recovery rates, and system integration (Andini et al., 2024).

On the economic front, pilot techno-economic analyses of chemical routes suggest feasible margins under certain feedstock purity and scale assumptions. However, industrial adoption still hinges on overcoming CAPEX/OPEX uncertainties and logistics costs (Andini et al., 2024; Speight et al., 2020). Human-centric automation, a key tenet of Industry 5.0, plays a pivotal role in improving worker safety and system acceptability (Fig. 5). Vision-based sorting, ergonomic workstation design, and collaborative robots reduce exposure to dust and repetitive tasks while supporting workforce reskilling into supervisory roles (Chivilò and Meneghetti, 2023; Costa, 2024).

Fig. 5. Key environmental impact metrics comparing advanced textile recycling with virgin material production and conventional waste handling (a); Quantitative improvements enabled by Industry 5.0 principles in textile recycling environments (b)

Despite positive trends, several gaps remain. There is little empirical evidence on robust defibering of multilayer textiles at scale. Few studies provide standardized TRL reporting or system-wide techno-economic models. Real-world pilots integrating AI-sorting, robotic handling, and human-centric operation remain rare, particularly for padded and upholstered items (Spyridis et al., 2024; Chattaraj et al., 2025).

Given the heterogeneity of multilayer waste, hybrid process chains are essential. High-purity mono-materials can be directed to chemical depolymerization, while contaminated or inseparable multilayers are better suited for mechanical defibering and conversion into functional nonwovens or composite boards. The Borsoi model's integration of Industry 5.0 principles, such as human-centric design, collaborative robotics, and adaptive digital twins reinforces its real-world applicability.

To enhance replicability, the literature suggests three key recommendations:

1. *Combine high-precision AI sorting with modular downstream processing tailored to item composition and contamination levels.*
2. *Apply Industry 5.0 design frameworks to ensure ergonomic, safe, and socially acceptable automation environments.*
3. *Prioritize transparent pilot-scale validation with complete LCA and techno-economic assessments (TEA) to guide scale-up.*

4. Conclusions

The Borsoi model offers a modular, scalable solution for recycling padded and upholstered textile waste, combining AI-based sorting, mechanical defibering, and Industry 5.0 principles. High classification accuracy (>95%) and hybrid process chains enable material recovery and valorization, even from complex, multilayer items. Human-centric automation enhances safety and workforce acceptance.

Beyond technical performance, the Borsoi system exemplifies the transition from traditional mechanized recycling toward adaptive, intelligent, and sustainable manufacturing ecosystems. By embedding digital twin architectures, predictive analytics, and real-time data exchange, the platform contributes to the creation of transparent and resilient textile recovery networks. Its modularity allows integration into regional or decentralized recycling infrastructures, promoting short supply chains and strengthening local circular economies.

The environmental implications are equally significant: zero-water sanitization, reduced energy use, and contamination rates below 1% position the system as an eco-efficient benchmark aligned with EU Green Deal targets and forthcoming EPR frameworks. The incorporation of Industry 5.0's human-centric philosophy ensures that automation is balanced with worker empowerment, health protection, and skill enhancement, fostering social sustainability alongside technological innovation.

To support full-scale deployment, future research should validate the model under industrial conditions through long-term pilot trials, comprehensive life cycle assessments (LCA), and techno-economic evaluations (TEA). Further optimization of AI algorithms for mixed-textile recognition and continuous monitoring of fiber quality across reuse cycles will be crucial to confirm durability and market readiness.

Ultimately, the Borsoi platform stands as a pioneering demonstrator of circular textile regeneration, bridging automation, digitalization, and human values, to advance a resilient, inclusive, and economically viable recycling paradigm consistent with evolving policy and market needs.

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